

Hybridization of solar thermal systems into architectural envelopes

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Abstract

Despite significant development in the performance and efficiency of solar thermal technology, little consideration has been given to its interaction within building envelopes, aside from mechanical fixing systems. The lack of solutions for the architectural integration of solar collectors and the complexity of their assembly process remain important barriers for the widespread adoption of this technology. An innovative approach is proposed in which solar collectors are not merely integrated into conventional building envelopes, but instead these envelopes are hybridized and activated to house solar thermal systems. This poses the challenge of adapting solar thermal technology to the capacities and limitations of architectural skins. The paper presents results from three ongoing projects. BATISOL and BASSE investigate the development of solar thermal technology so as to fulfil the functional, constructional and formal requirements of building skins. Façade assemblies are turned into active skins by integrating unglazed solar collectors in the place of conventional renders and claddings. RETROKIT explores the usage of renewable energy gains within an alternative environmental control strategy, by direct supply of heated air into the ventilation system. Finally, a discussion is presented on architectural, constructional and thermal performance aspects of these solutions, based on both design assessments and experimental data.

Keywords

active skin, integrated solar, hybridized solar, unglazed solar collector

1 INTRODUCTION

Boosted by energy procurement policies, the pursuit for lower energy costs, and the ultimate need to reduce primary energy consumption, building skins are experiencing an extraordinary development in recent years, incorporating a number of energy-related technologies with increased levels of efficiency. Beyond passive measures based on insulation and thermal mass, the most advanced envelope solutions integrate a range of active renewable technologies, combined with heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) devices and even information and communication technology (ICT) systems.

Solar energy in particular can provide a key input to the energy balance of the building, and technologies such as solar thermal and photovoltaic are experiencing a rapid development. However, solar modules are typically designed as autonomous technical elements, and often conflict with other elements of the building (envelope, structure, systems, etc.). Moreover, when these innovative solutions are engineered from a purely performance-based approach, they often conflict with the architectural expression of the building.

The lack of products and solutions for the architectural integration of solar collectors within façades, together with their complex assembly process and high investment costs, constitute barriers to the widespread use of solar thermal technology in building skins.

An innovative approach is currently in development, where solar modules are conceived and developed as construction components that fulfil all functional, constructional and formal requirements of building skins. This paper discusses results from ongoing research projects exploring strategies to integrate and/or hybridize solar thermal technology into building envelopes.

2 SOLAR THERMAL TECHNOLOGY

The satisfactory performance of a solar thermal system requires notable design efforts, extending beyond its energy harvesting surfaces and the performance levels of related HVAC devices. The delivery of energy-efficient solar systems is mostly bound to the design of a complete system that meets the needs of its users, profiting of an energy source of fluctuating nature, through a carefully planned storage and delivery system.

Solar systems are faced with intermittent energy availability (solar radiation, ambient temperature) and discontinuous energy needs (building occupation, domestic hot water needs, changes in heating temperature set point). This imposes the need for thermal storage in order to compensate for the seasonal discrepancy between supply and demand. Several experiences from the field demonstrate that combined solar systems, if properly sized, can provide a relevant increase in overall system efficiency. In (Cost-Effective, 2012) experience from simulation resulted in a coefficient of performance (COP) 30–40% higher than for regular air-source heat pumps. Within the 2Sol system, developed at ETH Zurich (Leibundgut, 2013), low-temperature input from photovoltaic/thermal collectors was used to regenerate a seasonal ground heat storage, reaching a COP above 8 in new buildings, and above 6 in retrofit (Haller, Sandoval, Nogueira, Ruggie, & Leibundgut, 2014).

In principle, solar thermal systems are able to absorb, transfer and store solar energy. Solar collectors are responsible for the first of these functions, while the absorbed heat is usually transferred through a fluid. For a given solar radiation level and ambient temperature (which are ultimately determined by local weather and climate), performance levels are fundamentally driven by the average temperature of the fluid. Therefore, the efficiency of solar thermal collectors can be broadly defined according to their type:

- Vacuum tube collectors suit high temperature applications such as solar cooling systems. In this technology, the absorber is suspended in vacuum and contained within glass tubes. The arrays of glass cylinders need to be placed within the building envelope. The most successful integration strategies incorporate the glass tubes into the design, for instance as parapets or screens for balconies (Fig. 3a).
- Glazed flat plate collectors constitute the most common technology. The absorber plate sits between a glass cover above (to allow solar radiation in) and an insulating layer behind (to minimise heat loss). A number of integration solutions for flat plate collectors are available in the market, commonly linked to specific cladding systems or lightweight façades (Fig. 3b).
- Unglazed collectors are the simplest technology of solar thermal collector, consisting only on an absorber that can be metallic (Fig. 3c) or polymer-based. Unglazed collectors are only sufficiently performing for applications that deliver fluid at lower temperatures. Currently, they are typically used for swimming pool heating systems, low temperature space heating or pre-heating of domestic hot water.

FIG. 1 Efficiency (η) of solar collectors depending on fluid-to-ambient temperature differential ($T_m - T_{amb}$) divided by incident solar radiation (G_{tot}). Source: (Giovanardi, 2012); see also (Duffie & Beckmann, 2013)

The efficiency of thermal systems is mostly related to the temperature at which heat is delivered. For solar systems, a lower output temperature results in a higher energy output for the same solar input. However, reduced service temperatures require larger surfaces in order to exchange the same amount of heat with the occupied space of buildings. Under this principle, low-exergy systems target low-temperature delivery systems such as radiant floors (Fig. 2). Other types of heat uses such as pool heating and domestic hot water heating are serviced at temperatures close to their set service temperatures. For the case of solar cooling systems, temperatures above 100 °C are recommended for thermally driven chiller systems.

FIG. 2 Temperature levels of solar collector technologies, compared to HVAC services in buildings

Despite their limitations, unglazed collectors constitute a promising solution for the widespread integration of solar systems in building envelopes. Their relatively low fluid temperature (Fig. 2) imposes the use of heat pumps, storage tanks and/or other auxiliary devices in order to ensure that delivered fluid temperatures suit the needs of building systems such as space heating or domestic hot water.

3 ARCHITECTURAL IMPACT OF SOLAR TECHNOLOGY IN BUILDING SKINS

The interaction of solar thermal systems into architectural projects faces not only technological barriers in the field of HVAC systems, or related to the aesthetics of the system itself, but also those related with the adaptation of the architectural solution to each specific building project. The implementation of solar systems requires a large envelope surface, resulting in a noticeable impact in the architectural expression of the building.

The authors propose the following overarching classification describing architectural strategies for the interaction of solar thermal systems with building envelopes:

- Addition: No consideration is given to the impact of thermal systems on the architectural quality of the building. Solar collectors are engineered as standalone elements and mechanically assembled over the building envelope. The system does not include a solution for its connection to the elements and systems of the building.
- Integration: Solar thermal systems are integrated within modular structures such as cladding systems or curtain walls, allowing for some dimensional flexibility in order to match the grid and composition of the façade. Collectors are usually glazed, and designed to conceal pipework and connections.
- Hybridization: Façade assemblies are hybridized with active thermal systems, by incorporating unglazed solar collectors within external renders and claddings. A neutral aesthetic impact is achieved, where users cannot differentiate between hybridized and ordinary building skins. These solutions are commonly combined with advanced HVAC systems, in which solar systems are connected with thermal storage, heat pumps, and/or low energy delivery systems such as radiant floors or thermal mass activation.

FIG. 3 Façade integration solutions for a) vacuum tube collectors (Schweizer Energie), b) flat plate collectors (Winkler Solarfassade), c) unglazed collectors (Energie Solaire, Toiture Solaire AS)

Despite the availability of an increased number of solutions for the architectural integration of solar systems (Fig. 3), these are still not widespread in the solar collector market. Most solutions result in a technification of the appearance of the façade, as only glazed or metal finishes are available. An extensive research on the architectural integration of solar systems in façades was carried out in (International Energy Agency, 2012).

FIG. 4 a) Capillary tubes within steel cladding system (SOLABS, 2006), b) render finish (Cost-Effective, 2012)

A number of research projects have focused on the development of hybridized solutions towards the activation of building envelopes without modifying their external appearance. Within (SOLABS, 2006) a steel façade cladding system was adapted for the integration of water-based capillary tubes on its internal side. Within (Cost-Effective, 2012) a façade system was developed based on external thermal insulation systems, in which capillary tubes were integrated within the external render finish, coupling the system with a heat pump for decentralized space heating.

4 CASE STUDIES

Tecnia has contributed to the conceptualization, design and testing of three innovative solar thermal solutions presented below. For their optimisation and validation in real usage conditions, experimental campaigns have been carried out at the KUBIK test facility (Garay, et al., 2015). KUBIK is located at Tecnia's premises in the Basque Country, close to the northern coastline of Spain (43°17'N 2°52'W), in a warm temperate climate representative of Central and Western Europe, corresponding to Cfb within the Köppen-Geiger classification (Kottek, Grieser, Beck, Rudolf, & Rubel, 2006).

FIG. 5 Pilot set-ups at south-facing façade of KUBIK test facility: (a) integrated solar air collector (RETROKIT, 2016), (b) hybridized sandwich-type steel envelope (BASSE, 2016)

4.1 GLAZED AIR SOLAR COLLECTOR FOR INTEGRATION IN ENERGY RETROFIT

The design of the glazed air solar collector developed within (RETROKIT, 2016) has been based on a technological framework consisting of an extruded aluminium frame and a rotating louvre system for the control of ventilation flows in the collector (Amundarain, et al., 2014). The collector is directly anchored into the existing façade, and integrates within an external render system for energy retrofit of existing buildings. The absorber is composed by a single aluminium sheet painted in black (Fig. 5a). The system can adapt its dimensions for adapting to particular project needs, following design criteria for curtain wall systems.

The system does not focus on a direct use of the collected energy; instead it integrates into a wider HVAC system, by directing outlet ducts to manifolds in the upper area of the façade. Several modules can be accommodated, in order to increase mass flow or output temperature as required by the HVAC system of the building.

An experimental campaign was carried out at the KUBIK test facility from January to June 2015. The test proved the capacity of the system to raise ventilation air temperature in sunny days within the heating season (Fig. 6), potentially allowing for a substantial reduction of heating loads in buildings.

FIG. 6 Results from experimental tests of (RETROKIT, 2016) at KUBIK test facility during March-May 2015: service temperature levels of solar collector (T_{outlet}) and temperature gain from ambient air ($T_{outlet} - T_{amb}$) as a function of incident solar radiation, for different times of day (11h, 13h, 15h, 17h)

4.2 UNGLAZED SOLAR COLLECTOR HYBRIDIZED INTO STEEL-BASED SANDWICH PANELS

Sandwich envelope systems offer a fast installation within limited cost. Although they were originally associated with industrial buildings, newly developed solutions with a metal finish are increasingly common in commercial and multi-rise residential buildings. Ventilated façades, widely adopted in the EU as a retrofit solution, commonly consist of a metal substructure and a cladding material that can be metal, stone, ceramic or phenolic, among others.

A number of projects such as (SOLABS, 2006) have investigated the integration of fluid loops within highly conductive cladding materials as the absorber of an unglazed collector. An innovative solution is developed within (BASSE, 2016) in which steel sandwich panels are used to integrate the pipework for an unglazed collector, using an additional external steel layer with a selective coating that maximizes the absorption properties (Fig. 5b).

One of the most remarkable advantages of this technology lies in its seamless integration between building envelope and solar thermal collector field. The observer cannot notice any difference between active and non-active sections of the building envelope.

Initial surface temperature measurements at the external skin (without fluid circulation) carried out at the KUBIK test facility demonstrated that values up to 72 °C can be achieved in a November hot day with maximums of 22 °C ambient temperature and 850 W/m² irradiance (Fig. 7 left). Once the fluid circulates through the collector, the temperature of the skin becomes lower thanks to the refrigeration action of this fluid. This continuously captured energy is deployed into a buffer tank. Fig. 7 right shows a representative day of June, with maximums of 25,3 °C ambient temperature and 435 W/m² irradiance. A maximum skin temperature of 46,9 °C is reached, with a thermal increase of 21,1 °C in the storage, heating up this thermal buffer up to 36,3 °C over 5,23 hours.

FIG. 7 Temperatures of ambient air (T_{amb}), skin (T_{skin}) and tank (T_{tank}) and solar irradiance (gray shaded area) for selected days measured during experimental test of (BASSE, 2016) at KUBIK test facility

The output temperature provided by the system is below service levels required for space heating and domestic hot water. This implies the use of a heat pump where the collector field is connected to its source. Once the sizing of the source-side storage is carried out correctly, the proposed layout provides a stable high temperature source for the heat pump, with a substantial increase of its performance when compared with benchmark heat pump technologies. Numerical and experimental technical assessments have demonstrated that this technological approach reaches the performance level of benchmark unglazed solar collectors.

4.3 UNGLAZED SOLAR COLLECTOR FOR HYBRIDIZATION INTO LIGHTWEIGHT FAÇADE SYSTEMS

Within the BATISOL project, a low-cost unglazed solar technology has been developed for seamless integration behind lightweight metal cladding systems. The collectors are modular and the design has been focused on optimising their assembly process. The integration with combined solar systems and heat pumps will provide thermal energy for heating and hot water through the use of a highly efficient technology.

Initially, a parametric study was carried out using finite element analysis within COMSOL Multiphysics software (Bonnamy, Raji, Lopez, & Garay, 2016), in order to establish an optimum geometry for the collector from a performance point of view. Results showed that the most influencing parameters determining the overall efficiency are (1) the width/depth ratio of the collector channels and (2) the spacing between these channels.

Results from simulation (Fig. 9) show good agreement with measurements from a test bench prototype. A full scale experimental test will be carried out in Bordeaux during 2017.

FIG. 8 Concept sketch of the solution developed within the BATISOL project

FIG. 9 Simulated performance of BATISOL solution as a function of temperature differential divided by solar irradiance (Bonnamy, Raji, Lopez, & Garay, 2016). The four scenarios combine an external surface of galvanised steel ($\alpha = 0,6$; $\epsilon = 0,2$) or matt black coating ($\alpha = 0,95$; $\epsilon = 0,95$) with low ($h = 5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$) or moderate ($h = 15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$) wind conditions

5 DISCUSSION

Although still under development and in early deployment scale, the field of integrated and hybridized solar thermal technologies is promising. Their underlying approach reaches far beyond the adaptation of solar thermal collectors to sizes and dimensions to match façade grids, leading into full envelope systems designed to absorb solar energy.

Three innovative technological solutions have been presented for the inclusion of solar renewable technology within building skins, each based on a different exploratory approach. The placement of solar collectors within the façade foregoes an optimum orientation/tilt in order to achieve an integrated solution that is better suited to the architectural requirements of façade design.

Glazed air collectors are a suitable solution for centralized or decentralized ventilation systems and can be integrated as part of retrofitting systems and kits. On the other hand, the hybridization of main building envelope systems (renders, steel-based cladding solutions and sandwich panels) allows for an efficient incorporation of unglazed collectors into combined solar systems. Experimental results are within a performance range that corresponds to the potential of the solar technologies developed within these projects, making use of renewable sources to achieve a substantial improvement in energy efficiency. Even if the assessed systems are still in development stage, it is expected that their lower complexity when compared to current market solutions should result in a reduction of investment, operation and maintenance costs.

In the following years, these technologies should develop into industrially and economically viable solutions with certified performance levels and relevant certifications, achieving full integration and hybridization into building skins.

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